

EU MAP WEBINAR

Protected natural sites: A constraint or an opportunity for mountain value chains?

HIGHLIGHTS REPORT

5 October 2023

On 5 October 2023, [AEIDL](#) organised the third [MOVING](#) EU Multi-Actor Platform (EU MAP) webinar on “[Protected Natural Sites: A Constraint or an Opportunity for Mountain Value Chains?](#)”. This online event gathered over 70 attendees from 25 countries with different backgrounds.

The main objectives of this webinar were:

- To provide an update about the proposal for a Nature Restoration Law in Europe, the ongoing discussions and upcoming steps;
- To present the [EU MAP study](#) on the perceived impacts of natural protected sites across the 23 MOVING mountain regions;
- To exchange knowledge, practices, and lessons learned on the implications of protected areas on mountain value chains.

Moderated by Carla Lostrangio (AEIDL), the webinar began with a presentation from Mar Delgado, MOVING’s coordinator, on the progress and latest results of the project, and a presentation from the MOVING Cluster N (‘Nature and Ecosystem Services’) highlighting the value of nature for mountain Value Chains of Sumava Region, Czechia.

Hence, interventions focused on the EU’s proposal for a [Nature Restoration Law](#), voted by the European Parliament on 12 July 2023 and is currently under review. This is one of the most important and ambitious attempts to foster nature’s protection and restoration in Europe, by promoting a change of its underlying legislative framework.

The [EU MAP study](#) on protected natural sites and its implications across the 23 MOVING Regions was presented by Blanca Casares, AEIDL. The study identified both limitations and opportunities and has shown that opportunities are perceived as outweighing possible limitations.

The event also featured presentations of two MOVING [Regions](#) of the project, namely the Austrian Alps and the Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains. These regions exemplified the close relations between natural sites and their mountain value chains.

Views and insights from attendees were collected through virtual breakout rooms and reported in the plenary. Then, the webinar ended with a round table discussion with representatives from UNIMONT and D.R.E.A.M. Italia with recommendations for policy actions that could enable better synergies between natural protected areas and mountain value chains.

ORGANISER:

 5 OCTOBER 2023

 ONLINE

 72 PARTICIPANTS
(research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.)

 25 COUNTRIES

 PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

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GETTING TO KNOW MOVING

MOVING Progress and Results

María del Mar DELGADO

MOVING Coordinator, University of Cordoba

Mar Delgado, Professor at the Department of Agriculture Economics at the University of Cordoba (Spain) and MOVING coordinator, presented the progress made and the results achieved since the latest [EU MAP meeting](#) in November 2022.

Funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, [MOVING](#) (MOuntain Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth) is a four-year project (2020-2024) with 23 partner organisations across 16 countries. MOVING aims to build capacities and co-develop relevant policy frameworks across Europe for the establishment of Value Chains that contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas to climate change and other threats, such as depopulation.

The project's research and activities have been built on the basis of the MOVING [Conceptual Analytical Framework](#) (Moretti et al. 2023). By bringing together Ostrom's Socio-Ecological System framework with the Value Chain framework, the MOVING Conceptual Analytical Framework proposes an integrated approach to characterise Value Chains' contribution to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas. This framework has been used to investigate mountain Value Chains of the [23 MOVING Regions](#), which are an essential component of the [MOVING Community of Practice](#).

Prof. Delgado presented the [Participatory Analysis of the Vulnerability of Land Use Systems](#), which has been one of the

MOVING results. This analysis was performed for the [23 identified Value Chains](#) in MOVING Regions and led to in-depth analyses of the vulnerability of land use systems in these mountain territories.

In the upcoming months, MOVING will produce a cross-case comparison of the MOVING Value Chains. With this respect, [five cluster topics](#) have been identified and used to group MOVING Value Chains. Namely, these are Demographic and Social Aspects; Innovation and Infrastructure; Territoriality, Cooperation and Governance; Nature and Ecosystem Services; Value and quality Products. A [survey](#) has been launched to assess how mountain Value Chains contribute to the sustainability and Resilience of mountain Socio-Ecological Systems.

On [6-8 November 2023](#), the five clusters will be performing a 5 cross-case scenario workshop and foresight analysis to identify recommendations for creating enabling environments in mountain areas. The outputs of this exercise will complement the 23 participatory scenario analyses carried out in MOVING Regions and the upcoming [Foresight workshop at the European level](#) (11 January 2023).

The results of the MOVING Foresight Scenario Analyses will be used to facilitate the [EU Foresight exercise](#) as well as to prepare the Policy Roadmap, both expected in 2024, as key milestones before the project's final conference in summer 2024.

MOVING Cluster on Nature and Ecosystem Services

Tomáš UHNÁK

Czech University of Life Sciences

In 2023, MOVING established [5 thematic clusters](#) to guide the analysis of barriers and enablers for thriving mountain Value Chains. Among these, the Cluster on Nature and Ecosystem Services is coordinated by the Czech University of Life Sciences and it includes [six mountain regions in Europe](#).

Tomáš Uhnák, PhD student at the Cluster on Nature and Ecosystem Services, illustrated the situation of the [Šumava mountain region](#), Czechia, which is one of the six regions of this Cluster. Located in the Southwestern part of Czechia, this region is also known as the "Green Roof of Europe" as it is heavily forested and contains a unique natural ecosystem.

The region is very much contested by an historical perspective. During the communist area, as the region was unattractive from agricultural exploitation, hence forest cooperatives were created to cultivate the land, but they failed to last longer. As a result, for a long time, the region turned to be mainly a natural area with a high level of biodiversity.

Today, the Šumava Region is characterise by a high variety of actors. Focus groups and interviews with local stakeholders (farmers, natural parks and tourists) show that these actors often have

different visions and interests on land use. For instance, farmers heavily rely on subsidies, whereas tourism demand for accessing natural areas. Droughts were identified as the main threat for this region, followed by demographic changes, inflation. Overall, the vulnerability of farmers is very high, and their adaptive capacity is very low.

Through MOVING, the Šumava Region conducted a foresight analysis to identify the most desirable scenario for this mountain area by 2050. High Nature Value agriculture emerged as the most relevant given its ability to deliver provide added value to the products, increasing scale, and food quality production. This scenario would entail a strong support to farmers for preserving natural resources and protecting the landscape, combined with strict regulation of the tourism sector.

Tomáš underlined that the diversification of farming activities, promotion of local production and better cooperation among local actors are all key aspects for the future development of this region. Stronger horizontal and vertical cooperation of actors (at all levels), as well as stronger stakeholder engagement, were also the needs articulated by local actors.

FEATURED SPEAKERS

Nature Restoration Law

Kenny MEGANCK
Institute for European Environmental Policy

Kenny Meganck, Senior Policy Analyst at the [Institute for European Environmental Policy](#) (IEEP), provided an update on the ongoing discussion for the EU's Nature Restoration Law. This Law stems from the [European Green Deal](#) (2019), which identifies ecosystem and biodiversity restoration as one of its main goals.

Through the [EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030](#), the EU Member States are expected to make voluntary pledges to reach 30% of protected land and 30% of protected sea. Whereas the Biodiversity Strategy is not politically binding, it included the proposal for the Nature Restoration Law, a key step for the EU to move from voluntarily commitments towards legally binding targets.

As recalled by Kenny Meganck, the *"benefits (to 2070) of restoring degraded terrestrial, freshwater and coastal ecosystem protected by the EU Habitats Directive are estimated at EUR 1,860 billion"* and ranges from health to social, economic, climate and provision of food-related benefits. Making the Nature Restoration Law as a regulation is a key milestone to ensure more uniformity across Member States and enforcement in the Courts.

On 12 July (2023), the proposal of the EU's Nature Restoration Law was accepted by the European Parliament, with severe amendments in the text and after strong debates. Three trilogues

between Commission, Council and Parliament are taking place to reach a compromise (July, 16 October, 16 November). An agreement is expected in early 2024.

Mr. Meganck underlined that the current proposal of the Law is less ambitious than its original version. In the current proposal of the EU's Nature Restoration Law, key articles for mountainous areas are Article 4 ('Habitat targets'), Article 7 ('Natural connectivity of rivers'), Article 9 ('Agro-ecosystems'), Article 10 ('Restoration of forest ecosystems').

In the amended text of the proposal by the European Parliament, he claims, weakened the legal targets. The requirements for non-deterioration of remaining healthy habitats and restored habitats, re-creation of lost habitats are binding mainly in Nature 2000 sites, while they are not required outside those sites. Article 9 was completely removed by the European Parliament, whereas Article 10 made binding the planting of 3 billion trees by 2030.

To conclude, Mr. Meganck stressed that the role of industry and landowners is crucial for nature restoration. To this end, an alignment of the Law and the post-2027 EU Budget is necessary, in particular through new funding streams in the Common Agricultural Policy, Horizon programme and the Cohesion Policy funds.

Natural Restoration Plans & Implementation at the Member State level

An CLIQUET
University of Ghent, Society for Ecological Restoration (SER) Europe Legal Working Group

An Cliquet, Professor of international environmental and biodiversity law at Ghent University, presented the terms for the implementation of the Natural Restoration Law at Member State level. She argued that European Commission's policy proposal was very holistic in its basis, legally sound and it will provide more leeway for sustainable human activities.

In the EU's Nature Restoration Law, each Member State is in charge to define its concrete restoration measures through Nature Restoration Plans. This is a new instrument which would provide clear obligations and deadlines to ensure the implementation of the Law.

The National Nature Restoration Plans should include measures up to 2050 and be grounded on science. The European Commission is responsible for assessing the Plans, whereas Member States shall revise them every decade. Overall, countries' contribution should restore 20% of land and sea areas at the EU level, by 2050. Yet, at the moment, the current proposal lacks an effort sharing mechanisms between Member States.

Article 11 and Article 12 provides details on the preparation and on the content of the National Restoration Plans, respectively. The main ingredients that shall be set up by the national Nature Restoration Plans are the area to be restored; synergies with climate change mitigation and adaptation efforts, as well as with disaster prevention; coordination with other existing measures, laws and framework, and with other national Restoration Plans; timing, monitoring, measures planned; financing needs.

The European Parliament's amendments, stressed Prof. Cliquet, weakened the Commission's proposal leading to a reduced ambition in restoration obligations, which would be inadequate to cope with climate and biodiversity crisis.

Furthermore, the amended proposal provides a wide margin of appreciation to Member States (which is what a Regulation should not do, as opposed to a Directive), and allow to prioritise socio-economic aspects to ecological aspects in the national Restoration Plans. Another crucial issue, yet to be solved, is finance as no dedicated funding is clearly earmarked in the draft Law and the role of CAP for nature restoration is so far overlooked.

FEATURED SPEAKERS

Stocktaking from the World Network of Mountain Biosphere Reserves

Roberto AQUERRETA

World Network of Mountain Biosphere Reserves

Roberto Aquerreta, environmental consultant supporting the Technical Secretariat of the [World Network of Mountain Biosphere Reserves](#) (WNMBR), presented key achievements of this network and its upcoming plans.

The term 'Biosphere Reserve' is a landscape management tool used to denote places for places for performing transdisciplinary research and testing, with the goal to manage interactions between social and ecological systems. Of 727 Biosphere Reserves existing today across the world, 65% contain mountain ecosystems.

In December 2021, the WNBR was launched to valorise mountain Biosphere Reserves by the [UNESCO's MAB Programme](#) and the Mountain Research Institute. As of today, this network counts 46 mountain Biosphere Reserves from 22 different countries, yet participation is also open to other actors than Biosphere Reserves.

The WNMBR aims at creating knowledge for management, creating research opportunities linked to mountain Biosphere Reserves, sharing best practices and knowledge sharing. Citizens and society are encouraged to be involved in this network and complement scientific research. Another goal of the WNMBR is to

attract financial resources for the development of the Network and the creation of new mountain Biosphere Reserves.

Several thematic areas are covered by the WNMBR. These ranges from biodiversity conservation and climate change to citizen science, sustainable resource management, demography and green economics, cultural values etc.

Mr. Aquerreta presented the WNMBR's [Roadmap for 2023-2025](#). The identified measures are grouped across three main work lines, namely "Research for Actionable Knowledge", "Support Adaptive Management" and "Empowerment and Engagement".

Presently, the WNMBR is conducting a survey to identify best practices that could be later transferred and scaled up within the Network. These practices cover the topics of climate change (adaptation, mitigation and resilience), biodiversity, and participation and socio-economic practices.

In the future, the WNBR will keep reinforcing the network of actors, enhancing knowledge exchange and promoting the roll-out of participatory practices in mountain areas.

RESULTS FROM THE MOVING STUDY

Impacts of Protected Natural Sites in MOVING Mountain Value Chains

Blanca CASARES

European Association for Innovation in Local Development (AEIDL)

Blanca Casares, Policy and Rural Development expert at the [EU Association for Innovation in Local Development](#) (AEIDL), presented key findings of her [study](#). The aim of the study was to investigate the presence of natural protected sites within the [23 MOVING Regions](#) and their impacts on mountain Value Chains, both positive and negative ones. This study was conducted in the framework of the [EU MAP](#), the EU-level component of the [MOVING Community of Practice](#) and published in April 2023.

Of the 23 surveyed territories, it emerged that 60% of the MOVING Regions have a natural protected site, in particular Nature 2000 sites and Protected Landscapes and Seascape sites. This designation can lead to both opportunities, for it increases the attractiveness of the area, but also presents constraints to economic development in mountain areas Value Chains.

This study shows that most surveyed participants (82.6%) argued the presence of natural areas is an opportunity as it brings economic, environmental, and social benefits. Key opportunities pointed out by respondents were tourism attractiveness (39,1%), followed by increased environmental resilience (34,8%), and enhanced Value Chains and food marketing (30,4%).

Yet, 43.5% of MOVING Regions said that protected natural sites are somehow a constraint to mountain Value Chains as they harshen regulations on business activity and prevention, land and resource use as well as restrict tourism and visitor management. As presented by Blanca Casares, regulatory barriers were perceived as a hindering factor by approximately 35% of surveyed respondents.

This study underlines the complex interactions between social and ecological systems in mountain areas and attempts to draw its interactions and potential synergies for mountain development.

TESTIMONIALS FROM MOUNTAIN VALUE CHAINS

Moderated by Carla Lostrangio, European Association for Innovation in Local Development

Sheep pasture farming in the Nature Park Almenland

Sandra KARNER

Coordinator of the Austrian Alps Reference Region, Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture (IFZ)

Sandra Karner, Senior Research at the Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture (IFZ) illustrated the impacts of the Almenland Natural Park on the [Austrian Alps' lamb value chain](#).

Located in one of the largest contiguous low-alpine pasture areas in Europe, this region contains two Natura 2000 sites, one Nature Reserve and one Bird Reserve. The region is economically dependent on forestry, agriculture and tourism, and it is characterised by diversified gastronomy and a rich cultural heritage.

The Almenland Natural Park also hosts a flourishing community. In 1995, the [multi-actor Weize cooperative](#) primarily specialised in meat processing facilities and dairy was funded and, in 2022, it counted approximately 320 members and 150 farms. The Weize cooperative seized the opportunities delivered by the LEADER programme to implement more environmentally conscious practices, ensure better water management and promote slow tourism.

"Natural landscapes are an essential part of the region", emphasised Sandra Karner as they bring both positive ecological and social impacts. However, she also pointed out that today wildlife conflicts, forest encroachment and reforestation are among the biggest threats to the activities of the Weize cooperative.

Traditional practices and regulatory frameworks are sometimes not aligned with these changes in the natural habitats, turning them into hindering factors to the lamb value chain. An example is the increase of wildlife, in particular bears and wolves, which found local farmers unprepared as shepherd dogs have never been a traditional practice of this region.

Find out more about the Austrian Alps Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional Multi-Actor Platform (MAP), [here](#).

Interactions between natural protected sites and the ecotourism value chain in Romania

Alina ALEXA

Member of the coordination team of the Southern Romanian Carpathian mountains reference region, Highclere Consulting

Alina Alexa, Communication Specialist at the Highclere Consulting, unveiled the interactions between natural protected sites and the [ecotourism value chain](#) in the Southern Romanian Carpathians.

"It is essential to have the opportunity to have well-preserved natura areas for certified ecotourism", she emphasised. Since 1990s, several projects on the conservation of large carnivores were running in the Southern Carpathians. These projects primarily focused on protecting, monitoring and raising awareness of the added value of large carnivores' presence for regional businesses. Large steps were carried out on ecological maintenance was carried out and the supply of services (accommodation, hotels, leisure and nature activities) associated with ecotourism. Consequently, an association to promote certified ecotourism and 10 ecotourism destinations were established.

"This led to increasing tourism and accommodation services", explained Alina Alexa and, even today, tourism activities rely a lot on

this activity. She argued that regional actors understood that nature protection can bring added value and stimulate new economic activities. Environmentally protected regions have had a clear impact on maintaining the population in the community, providing professional opportunities, etc.

Some conflicts exist with respect to strict regulations and limitations on land use, in particular for the building sector. Yet, the main struggle is to find financial resources to protect those Socio-Ecological Systems and inform people on the advantages these interactions between natural protected sites and economic activities can secure.

Find out more about the Southern Romanian Carpathian mountains Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional Multi-Actor Platform (MAP), [here](#).

VIRTUAL BREAKOUT ROOMS

Limits and opportunities linked to natural sites' presence

The core discussion continued with participants through virtual breakout rooms. Participants were asked to give their feedback on limits and opportunities linked to the presence of natural protected areas based on their own experience, as well as adequate policy measures to address them.

Overall, participants agree with limitations and opportunities identified by the AEIDL's study and speakers. Some participants stressed wildlife conflicts and lack of knowledge on how to manage those tensions as a key constraint to farming activities in mountains. This often results into 'irrational' fear and is fueled by detrimental media narratives.

Some participants also pointed out that whereas legislation for natural protected areas is clear and well-defined, monitoring and evaluation and coordination of protected areas should be strengthened. More binding measures in the management of protected natural areas have been welcomed by some of the participants. Financing was also mentioned several times as a key barrier to mountain development.

Participants emphasised the need to raise awareness of the benefits due to the presence of natural sites for local actors, such as better ecosystem quality and marketing of local products, in particular among practitioners and farmers. To this extent, it would be appreciated to acknowledge the added value of local products connected to natural protected areas and ecological practices through certification schemes.

Participants commended that natural protected areas should be increasingly perceived as open laboratories and testbed areas for research. Genuine multi-level dialogue, with a strong involvement of national authorities/agencies and local administrators, should be reinforced to valorise the Socio-Ecological interactions of mountain ecosystems.

There is a need for better educational programs on the positive outcomes from the interactions between natural protected areas and mountain Value Chains. Capacity building and self-perception should be enhanced and supported by more consistent financing streams.

<p>Do you agree with the limits and opportunities that emerged from the EU MAP study and the testimonials?</p> <p><i>Is there something else that should be added/underlined?</i></p>	Lack of sufficient contracted staff in these spaces and the presence of many volunteer staff	Protected areas can be seen as laboratories for research and testing their own limitations	Lack of state funding for natural areas. Need to apply for European Life-type projects	Skills and personal knowledge and capacity
	Consider linking national restoration plans with mandatory management plans for existing wilderness areas	Coexistence with large carnivores	Initiatives that bring people together: a platform for networking, and cooperation	A lot of irrational fear: need for more fact-based & constructive discussion
<p>What policy measures should be taken according to you?</p>	Strengthen governance (in particular the role of local administrations)	Coordinate available funding for the natural spaces	Favouring the link between the local community and these areas, for example by improving employability	Landscape resources management
	Boost living laboratories in these areas	Multi-level intervention/tools, depending on the topic and on type of protected areas	Unification of certification schemes	Better engagement from national policy/decision makers

WRAP-UP ROUND TABLE

With Stefano Sala (UNIMONT and member of Euromontana) and Tommaso Campedelli (D.R.E.A.M. Italia)

Two guest experts and lead partners of the EU-funded projects on mountain areas were invited to make their final contributions on the topic covered by this webinar. Stefano Sala, Project Manager at the **UNIMONT** Centre and lead part of the Horizon Europe **MountResilience**, pointed out that land use conflicts are likely to raise across mountain areas, particularly in the tourism sector. For this reason, co-development and stakeholder engagement is crucial to help stakeholders understanding the environmental, ecologic and social value of natural protected areas.

According to Mr. Sala, future discussions should focus on how to involve stakeholders in the development of natural management plans at local value, as well as on the management of natural areas and its conflicts. Furthermore, conversations should be moved forward with policy makers, and make them informed about scientific research.

Tommaso Campedelli, Scientific Expert at D.R.E.A.M. Italia and Coordinator of the **LIFE ShepForBio project**, underlined that protected areas are important to increase economic activity to mountain areas, but for this to happen, the right conditions should be ensured.

First of all, in several European natural sites, conservation is linked to human activities, such as pastoralism and other traditional activities. Therefore, proper training opportunities should be offered for these activities to be kept on to managers and teams working in these natural areas. In addition, it is needed to improve communication of the issues and opportunities in these areas, especially to the general public. Community involvement in the management and decision-making of these areas should be also reinforced as a leeway for a more integrated win-win approach.

Stefano Sala from UNIMONT and member of Euromontana and Carla Lostrangio from AEIDL (at the top), and Tommaso Campedelli from D.R.E.A.M. Italia (at the bottom)

CLOSING REMARKS

Carla Lostrangio (European Association for Innovation in Local Development)

Carla Lostrangio, Rural and Territorial Development Expert at AEIDL and main facilitator of this event, closed the meeting with her key takeaways from this webinar. First, ongoing policy developments show a progressive transition towards an enabling legal framework in favor of natural protection and restoration. This enormous progress should be continued and pushed for, though the ongoing risk of softening the ambitions at European level is high.

Second, positive impacts linked to the presence of natural protected areas on mountain Value Chains outweigh negatives ones and they are both environmental and socio-economic. Testimonials

from MOVING Regions, breakout discussions as well as expert contributions all underline these numerous benefits.

Third, more adequate policy measures, as well as training opportunities and community engagement are needed to unlock the added value of natural sites for mountain development. To this end, policy measures should be promoted to acknowledge the added value of natural sites for the mountain and lowland communities and to build a multi-level governance able to deal both with opportunities and tensions linked to complex interactions of these unique Socio-Ecological Systems.

Do you want to know more about the project and the community? Find more information, [here](#).
Join the EU MAP by expressing your interest, [here](#).
Or sign up for the newsletter, [here](#).

ANNEX

Internal session of EU MAP members

Taking advantage of the webinar, MOVING organised an internal session welcoming its EU MAP members and interested parties. Approximately 15 participants joined this session, which was designed to provide a comprehensive overview of the accomplishments achieved since the [latest EU MAP webinar](#), on November 2022.

As of September 2023, the total number of members of the EU MAP was 83, of which 55% were women and 45% were men, reflecting balanced gender representation. Notably, alongside strong representation from researchers, the platform also includes various other stakeholders, such as NGOs, policy authorities, and individuals from EU-funded projects.

Carla Lostrangio, Rural and Territorial Expert at AEIDL and EU MAP coordinator, presented a summary of the activities conducted in the framework of the EU MAP since the project's start. These include:

- 🌐 5 contributions submitted to EU open consultations on policy discussions relevant to mountain areas on [restoring sustainable carbon cycles](#), [EU's Long-Term Vision for rural areas](#), [brain drain](#), [sustainable EU food systems](#), and [agri-food system transition](#);
- 🌐 The organisation of 3 webinars for presenting MOVING's results, as well as transferring knowledge and exchange stakeholders' views;
- 🌐 The publication of the ["Women move Europe's mountains" booklet](#), highlighting the pivotal role of women in mountain communities to celebrate International Mountain Day 2022;
- 🌐 The production of a [study](#) exploring the limitations and opportunities associated with the presence of protected sites in MOVING Regions.

What are the upcoming activities of the EU MAP?

"As the project is turning towards its end, we look forward a more active and tight collaboration with the EU MAP", said Carla Lostrangio. The project's end is officially planned by August 2024, whereas its final conference will take place earlier in the summer 2024.

By then, a number of MOVING's results will be published and available for discussion and final review, before being presented to the European Commission. Among these, the most relevant ones are the MOVING Foresight Synthesis Report & Repertoire of Strategic

Options, the MOVING Roadmap and Policy Recommendations and the final version of MOVING Conceptual Framework.

Therefore, the EU MAP looks forward to several engaging activities in the upcoming months. These activities include:

- 🌐 [European Foresight Workshop "Shaping the future for resilient mountain areas"](#): Scheduled for January 11, 2024, in Brussels.
- 🌐 An EU MAP Webinar on MOVING Foresight Results and Strategic Options. Date to be confirmed but likely to take place in February or March 2024.
- 🌐 An EU MAP Webinar on MOVING Policy Roadmap. Date to be confirmed but likely to take place in April-May 2024.
- 🌐 Interviews with EU MAP Members: These interviews will complement open consultations on policy recommendations and insights.
- 🌐 MOVING Final Conference: The grand culmination of the MOVING project will possibly be held in June 2024 in Brussels.

The EU MAP members were also invited to actively participate in the activities within the [5 MOVING Clusters](#). From January to May 2024, they are welcomed to engage in a comparative analysis of the vulnerability, resilience, and sustainability of Value Chains for each cluster. The aim is to identify main success and failure factors against specific vulnerability contexts.

The internal session concluded with a discussion aimed at fostering collaborative efforts, active involvement in MOVING activities, and identifying particular topics for further discussion and consideration at the EU level.